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Pharmaceutical Effects of Trans-Cinnamaldehyde Nanoparticles on Cancer Types

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Abstract: Cancer research has been intensively ongoing for years, particularly in the field of treatment. Despite the development of numerous chemotherapeutic agents, a definitive cure has yet to be achieved. One of the major obstacles in treatment is the tumor microenvironment, which plays a critical role in cancer progression and therapy resistance. This microenvironment facilitates metastasis to healthy tissues and contributes to the development of multidrug resistance (MDR) against existing chemotherapeutic agents. Therefore, developing nanotechnological chemotherapeutic agents capable of bypassing the tumor microenvironment while minimizing systemic side effects is of great importance. Studies on the biological activities of cinnamaldehyde are quite popular. This review focuses on cinnamaldehyde-loaded nanoparticles used in cancer studies.

Introduction

Cancer is a leading cause of death worldwide, and the need for effective treatments with few side effects is growing. Critical obstacles to cancer treatment are drug insensitivity and resistance (Bilici and Akkoç, 2025). Multidrug resistance (MDR), is a primary factor in the inadequacy of existing chemotherapeutic methods. The excessive activity of xenobiotic mechanisms that occurs with cancer progression, resulting in the release of chemotherapy agents into the cell, adaptation in DNA repair mechanisms, growth factors, and genetic factors, all contribute to the development of MDR (Bukowski et al., 2020).

Another key factor contributing to MDR is the tumor microenvironment itself. In addition to the extracellular matrix (ECM), it harbors various structural cells that enable cancer cell survival and invasion. This complex structure functions as a shield that impedes the direct access of chemotherapeutic agents to cancer cells, promoting tumor heterogeneity. Furthermore, the increased activity of ABC (ATP-Binding Cassette) Transports in the cell membrane, especially P-gp (permeability glycoprotein), causes the drug to be released out of the cell without showing its effect or not to be taken into the cell at all (Duan et al., 2023). Immune evasion and cancer metastasis are also closely linked to this microenvironment (Peng et al., 2024).

The use of existing chemotherapeutic agents is limited due to their short half-life and their damage to healthy cells and tissues, and therefore nanomedical agents have become a focus for use in treatment strategies (Wei et al., 2021). Nanoparticles are proposed to target tumors through two main strategies: passive and active targeting. In passive targeting, nanoparticles exploit the leaky and disorganized vasculature of tumors to accumulate in tumor tissue. In contrast, active targeting involves ligand-specific delivery directly into cancer cells. The types of nanoparticles utilized in cancer therapy include dendrimer-based, polymeric, calcium-phosphate (single or combined), magnetic, quantum dots, silica, gold, carbon, liposomes, solid lipid, fullerenes, iron oxide nanocrystals, and cyclodextrin nanosponges. Additionally, lipid nanoparticles loaded with siRNA or miRNA are being explored for both therapeutic and imaging purposes (Awasthi et al., 2018). Their ability to selectively target cancer cells without harming normal ones and bypass P-gp-mediated resistance (Cho et al., 2008) makes them highly attractive in cancer research.

Cancer Effects of Trans-Cinnamaldehyde Nanoparticles

Cinnamaldehyde, a naturally occurring aromatic compound constituting approximately 65% of cinnamon extract, has gained significant attention in cancer research as well as the food industry. It is known for its ability to induce apoptosis, inhibit angiogenesis, and affect key processes related to cancer metastasis. Cinnamaldehyde also exhibits antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties (Peng et al., 2024). It triggers apoptosis through interactions with the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway, mitochondria, and cell death receptors (Banerjee, 2023). In lung adenocarcinoma cell lines A549 and NCI-H1650, as well as in mouse models, it was found to initiate apoptosis by interfering with the cell cycle. In human colorectal carcinoma cells (HCT-116), it not only induced apoptosis but also suppressed drug resistance-related genes. In ovarian carcinoma cell lines SKOV3 and A2780, it induced G2/M cell cycle arrest (Peng et al., 2024).

Previous studies on the use of cinnamaldehyde in nanomedicine report the following findings: In HepG2 hepatocellular carcinoma cells, nanoparticles loaded with suberin, trans-cinnamaldehyde, and paclitaxel affected the cell cycle (Liakos et al., 2019). Hybrid nanoparticles composed of lactobionic acid, doxorubicin, chitosan, and cinnamaldehyde (DOX-CLA, DOX-CCA, DOX-CLC) showed antitumor effects by inducing apoptosis (Zhou et al., 2022). Trans-cinnamaldehyde-loaded chitosan submicron particles (CSMP), a biopolymer-

based system, exhibited cytotoxic effects on HeLa cervical adenocarcinoma cells compared to MDCK epithelial model cells, suggesting their potential for chemotherapeutic drug delivery (Barrera et al., 2024).

Despite recent advances in cancer treatment, the success of metastatic breast cancer treatment is not at the desired level (Bilici et al., 2025). 4T1 breast tumor mouse models, it was found that copper-alanine nanoparticles (CACG) loaded with glucose oxidase and cinnamaldehyde increased oxidative stress by inducing ferroptosis and contributed to the activity of immune cells (Song et al., 2023); nanoparticles designed as double-layers with an inner mesoporous silica structure loaded with cinnamaldehyde and IR780 and an outer platelet membrane-coated nanoparticles (PSCI) increased oxidative stress (Huang et al., 2021); and a nanoplatform (ECPCP) designed to be encapsulated with the elesclomol-copper compound cinnamaldehyde and polyethylene glycol to activate the intracellular copper-induced death mechanism cuproptosis pathway inhibited tumor growth and accumulation both in vivo and in vitro in 4T1 models (Wu et al., 2024).

In vivo studies on lung tumors showed that cinnamaldehyde-loaded polydopamine-based hybrid nanoparticles (CACuPDA) enhanced anti-PD-L1 activity, thereby improving immune checkpoint blockade and positioning themselves as potential therapeutic agents (Jiang et al., 2025). SN-38 and JQ-1-loaded nanoparticles formulated with linoleic acid and cinnamaldehyde (SJNP) accelerated ROS-mediated mitochondrial dysfunction and apoptosis in murine triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) models (Zheng et al., 2024). Dual pH-sensitive chitosan nanoparticles loaded with cinnamaldehyde and doxorubicin (DCCA/DOX-NPs) were developed to overcome MDR in MCF7/ADR breast cancer cells, demonstrating high cytotoxicity and potential for MDR tumor treatment (Chen et al., 2022).

In another breast cancer study, mesoporous silica nanoparticles loaded with cinnamaldehyde and doxorubicin were modified with hyaluronic acid and coated with graphene oxide (MSNCA@GODOX-HA). These nanoparticles induced apoptosis via mitochondrial pathways and exhibited higher toxicity in MCF-7 cells compared to H9c2 cardiomyocyte cells (Dong et al., 2020). For lung cancer, nanoparticles composed of curcumin and cinnamaldehyde-loaded chondroitin sulfate were synthesized, which increased ROS levels, disrupted mitochondrial homeostasis, and inhibited tumor growth in A549 and H226 cells (Wang et al., 2025). Cinnamaldehyde and docetaxel-loaded nanoparticles (DTX/FA-CA-Oxi- α CD) exhibited antitumor and antimetastatic effects in 4T1 and MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell lines and improved anti-PD-1 antibody efficacy (Wang et al., 2023). In HCT116 colon cancer models, HCPT-CA (10-hydroxycamptothecin and cinnamaldehyde) nanoparticles facilitated cell death and drug uptake (Zhao et al., 2019). Cinnamaldehyde-loaded DTX/RGD nanoparticles inhibited tumor growth and induced apoptosis in in vitro and in vivo 4T1 models (Yao et al., 2023). A chitosan nanocarrier loaded with camptothecin and cinnamaldehyde (CACPT) showed promise for intravesical bladder cancer treatment (Liu et al., 2025). Lastly, copper-containing mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (Cu-MBGN) were shown to induce minimal toxicity in healthy BEAS-2B lung epithelial cells compared to A549 and H1299 cancer cells, highlighting their potential use as radiosensitizers in non-small cell lung cancer (He et al., 2025).

Conclusion

Research into cancer treatment remains popular because traditional chemotherapy methods, in addition to the damage caused by multidrug resistance in cancer cells, only slightly prolong patient survival. Because nanomedical products are designable, they may offer hope for addressing the challenges that complicate cancer treatment. Of course, there is an urgent need for increased research in this area and testing on more cancer types.

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